

PRESSURE CASTING OF FIBER-REINFORCED METALS

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ABSTRACT

The work reported herein investigates the infiltration of molten aluminum into a network of preheated fibers using an infiltration apparatus which allows continuous measurement of the position of the metal as it infiltrates a preform of "Saffil" fibers. Measurements of the permeability and infiltration length indicate a strong dependence on fiber volume fraction and fiber temperature, and a weaker dependence on metal temperature. Experimental evidence indicates that in the presence of metal superheat, solid metal formed at the infiltration front remelts over a distance in the composite. A simple lower bound estimation of this distance is proposed. Results of permeability measurements indicate a solidification mechanism for the metal in this work that differs from the uniform fiber coating mechanism proposed by other investigators.

INTRODUCTION

Much of the recent interest in fiber-reinforced metals has centered around alumina fibers. Imperial Chemical Industries has developed a δ - Al_2O_3 fiber specifically aimed at MMC applications, known as "Saffil" RF grade [1]. The fiber is $3\mu\text{m}$ in diameter and for the purposes of MMC fabrication is chopped, milled and sized to give a preselected range of lengths.

Clyne and Bader [2] recently studied the squeeze casting method of fabricating MMC's using "Saffil" fibers and aluminum base matrices. Using measured experimental variables, they described the processing sequence and temperature distributions in the preform as well as a fiber packing density gradient due to preform deformation. Fukunaga and co-workers [3] infiltrated a devitroceramic fiber with pure aluminum using conventional die casting equipment. They found that when the metal or fiber temperatures were too low, or the infiltration pressure too low, then poorly infiltrated or very porous castings were produced. If the temperatures were too high, then excessive fiber/metal reaction caused poor castings. Finally, if the plunger speed was too high then the preform was deformed upon infiltration.

Nagata and Matsuda wrote a series of papers studying particulate reinforced pure metals. Using squeeze casting techniques, they determined a critical preheating temperature (c.p.t.) of the preform, defined as the temperature above which the particles must be heated in order to achieve complete infiltration [4,5,6]. Focussing on the infiltration process itself, Fukunaga and Goda [7] studied the infiltration of pure aluminum into continuous glass fiber bundles.

Using a squeeze casting apparatus, they empirically found a relationship between infiltration length and squeeze pressure, fiber temperature and ram speed. They then proposed a model of the infiltration process based on the heat balance between the molten metal and the fiber bundle. By postulating that a layer of solid metal uniformly coats the fibers of a cold preform, they successfully predicted the effects of fiber preheat temperature on the permeability of the fiber bundle during infiltration. Evidence of the existence of this layer of solid metal was further supplied in another study by the same authors [8].

In this work, results are presented on the influence of various parameters on the infiltration of a preform of alumina fibers by molten aluminum. We treat herein the case of a matrix of commercial purity aluminum as part of an ongoing effort at MIT to study the infiltration behavior of both pure metals and alloys [9].

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The matrix material, commercial purity 99.9% aluminum, was unidirectionally infiltrated into preforms of Saffil alumina fibers with a pressure caster, designated herein as a hydrostatic pressure infiltration device (HPID). The operating principle behind the HPID is to use pressurized gas to force molten metal into an evacuated die. Figure 1 is a sketch of the device. It consists of two main components: the pressure vessel, containing the melt furnace and crucible, and the cap, attached to which are the control valves and the die. There are also feedthroughs for thermocouples, power leads, and a pressure transducer. The die is attached to the center of the cap and can be evacuated.

To operate the device the cap is placed on the pressure vessel, immersing the bottom of the die in the molten metal. The vessel is then pressurized with nitrogen, forcing the metal up through the die and into the fibers. The metal and the fibers do not come in contact until infiltration begins, which enables accurate and independent control of the fiber and metal temperatures. In addition, because of the design of the device the die need only sustain the compressive stresses imposed by the pressurized gas; heavy-walled metal dies common to other pressure casters are replaced with a quartz tube.

Figure 1- Schematic drawing of pressure caster.

Used with the HPID is a technique developed to measure the position of the molten metal front as it moves through the fiber preform during infiltration. This is achieved by inserting a SiC filament between the preform and the quartz tube mold. A potential is applied between the filament and the metal crucible, with the molten metal acting as a switch to close the circuit. A chart recorder then measures the potential drop across the SiC filament over time. As the metal infiltrates the preform the potential measured across the filament decreases due to the decrease of the effective electrical length of the SiC filament. Monitoring the potential drop during infiltration allows a calculation of the position of the metal front and its velocity over time.

Some experiments were performed using molten aluminum followed by lead to observe the infiltration behavior of the first portion of aluminum that enters the preform. In these experiments a 1.5 gram piece of aluminum is placed in the bottom of the quartz tube and floated on a bath of superheated molten lead before infiltration.

Metallographic preparation of composite samples was achieved by polishing with an automatic polisher with diamond paste on hard synthetic cloth, followed by a final polish with magnesium oxide on a soft billiard-type cloth. The samples were chemically etched to reveal grains by immersing for 2-3 seconds in an etch pitting solution of 50ml. nitric acid, 47ml. hydrochloric acid, and 3ml. hydrofluoric acid. Observation of the samples under cross-polarized light accentuates the etch pits and readily shows differences in their orientation across different grains. An example is provided in figure 2.

RESULTS

Experiments were performed to determine the effect of fiber temperature, metal temperature, and fiber volume fraction on the infiltration behavior of molten aluminum. Specific permeability of the fiber preform may be calculated from the following equation:

$$K = \mu \frac{dL}{dt} \frac{L}{P}$$

The experimental apparatus allows the continuous monitoring of L , dL/dt , and P during infiltration, so permeability may be calculated from experimental data. Curves showing the specific permeability as a function of processing parameters are given in figure 3. Permeability is measured near the beginning of each experiment as we find that after 4-5 seconds peripheral cooling effects due to the mold occur, causing choking and a decrease in measured permeability. The processing parameters influenced the final infiltration length in a manner analogous to the permeability K .

Experiments were performed using molten aluminum and lead as described above. While the aluminum solidifies in the preform during infiltration, the lead flows into those volumes not occupied by the aluminum thus allowing observation of the volumes where the aluminum first flowed. The photomicrograph in figure 4 shows the results of an experiment performed with the metal at 60°C superheat. We note the existence of a region at the base of the composite where the aluminum has been entirely replaced by lead. At the end of the experiment, therefore, this region was entirely liquid. Above this region lead and aluminum coexist in the matrix indicating that some aluminum was retained by the fibers since it was "overtaken" by lead. To be retained by the fibers, this aluminum must have been solid. Indication of a two-zone structure in cast aluminum matrix composites could also be found when the superheat was

Figure 2- Photomicrograph of etch pitted sample viewed under cross-polarized light. Note difference in orientation of pits across different grains.

Figure 4- Photomicrograph of infiltration by aluminum followed by lead. Dark regions are lead, light regions are aluminum. Infiltration occurred upwards.

Figure 5- Photomicrograph of etch pitted composite viewed under cross-polarized light. Infiltration occurred upwards.

Figure 6- Photomicrograph of etch pitted composite viewed under cross-polarized light. Note the many orientations of etch pits in the volume shown.

A

B

C

Figure 3- Effect of processing parameters on specific permeability of composite.
 A: Fiber temperature, B: Fiber volume fraction, C: Metal temperature.

sufficiently high to yield a region of large columnar grains in the upstream portion of the composite, figure 5. On the same sample, in the vicinity of the infiltration front, the microstructure is shown by the photomicrograph in figure 6 where many orientations of etch pits in a small volume indicate a fine grained matrix.

DISCUSSION

With an initial fiber preform temperature T_f , above the melting point of the metal T_M , the problem is one of pushing the liquid metal through a porous body with three effects opposing fluid flow:

1) A pressure drop due to capillary forces. In what follows, these are neglected compared to viscosity effects in the flowing metal. This assumption is mostly made for lack of adequate data on surface energies pertaining to the case at hand. Also, since the metal will first flow into wider channels of the preform [10], the fact that the porous region was small in all samples with the unalloyed metal is an indication that the pressure drop due to capillary forces must be small compared to the applied pressure.

2) A pressure drop due to friction of air flowing through the fibers ahead of the metal. Due to the low viscosity of air compared to that of aluminum, this will also be neglected.

3) A pressure drop due to friction effects in the liquid metal flowing through the fiber preform. The Reynolds number, Re , for fluid flow through a porous body is [11]:

$$Re = \frac{\rho_f (1 - V_f) d_f}{\mu V_f} \frac{dL}{dt}$$

where μ is the viscosity of the metal, V_f is the fiber volume fraction, d_f is the fiber diameter, L is the length of composite infiltrated at time t and ρ_f is the fiber density. Using data for the fibers, infiltration velocity and metal under study, Re is less than 0.1, which proves that flow of the metal into the preform is laminar ($Re_{critical} = 2$) [11]. The equation relating the metal flow rate with the applied pressure is therefore the Hagen-Poiseuille equation :

$$(1 - V_f) \frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{1}{4.2 \mu} \frac{(1 - V_s)^3}{V_s^2} \frac{1}{S_o^2} \frac{\Delta P}{L} \quad (1)$$

where V_s = volume fraction of the solid phase, S_o = surface area of the solid phase per unit volume of solid and ΔP = pressure drop over the infiltration length L . With assumptions 1) and 2) above, ΔP equals the applied pressure P . By definition of the specific permeability K , equation (1) yields :

$$K = \frac{(1 - V_s)^3}{4.2 V_s^2} \frac{1}{S_o^2} \quad (2)$$

When the fiber preform temperature is below the melting point of the metal, heat will be exchanged between the cold fibers and the hot metal. Given the small diameter of the fibers (3 μm), this heat exchange is quasi-instantaneous, so the fiber and metal temperatures can safely be assumed equal at any point within the infiltrated composite. At the infiltration front, therefore, the same liquid metal will be cooled very rapidly by the successive fibers it encounters. The temperature at the infiltration front therefore reaches the fiber preform

temperature T_f or the melting point of the metal T_m , whichever is highest. If $T_f < T_m$ the fibers will necessarily be heated to T_m by the enthalpy generated by the transformation of some liquid into solid, with evolution of latent heat H such that

$$(1 - V_f) H \rho_m f_s = c_f \rho_f V_f (T_m - T_f) \quad (3)$$

where f_s is the volume fraction solid formed in the metal and ρ_m is the metal density. The solid phase thus formed will be retained by the fine network of fibers and the liquid metal will therefore flow past, to form more solid metal downstream as it encounters new cold fibers. There is thus constant formation of solid at the infiltration front; behind the infiltration front there exists a region where the metal matrix contains a uniform volume fraction of solid f_s and where the temperature is constant at T_m , assuming equilibrium at the liquid-solid interface. The existence of this semi-solid matrix region is proven experimentally by the aluminum - lead infiltration experiment, figure 4.

A - Negligible metal superheat. If the metal temperature T_M is equal to T_m , the volume fraction solid f_s in the matrix is constant throughout the infiltrated composite and is given by equation (3). V_s in equations (1) and (2) therefore becomes:

$$V_s = V_f \left(1 + \frac{c_f \rho_f (T_m - T_f)}{H \rho_m} \right) \quad (4)$$

Fukunaga and Goda postulated that the solid forms as a uniform coating on the fibers. The term S_o in equations (1) and (2) therefore becomes:

$$S_o = \frac{4 \sqrt{V_f}}{d_f \sqrt{V_s}} \quad \text{and by insertion into equation (2); } K = \frac{(1 - V_s)^3}{V_s V_f} \frac{d_f^2}{32} \quad \text{is obtained}$$

after substitution of a factor 2 in place of 4.2 in equations (1) and (2) above. This equation agreed well with permeability measurements they performed at various fiber preform temperatures T_f [7], and as mentioned above, they confirmed their geometrical assumption in related experiments [8]. Their equation does not agree with data collected in this work, however. Permeabilities calculated with their equation are about half an order of magnitude larger than measured permeabilities given in figures 3-a and 3-b. Furthermore, K values measured in this work decrease with increasing V_s - or, equivalently, increasing f_s - more rapidly than predicted by Fukunaga and Goda's model. The discrepancy by half an order of magnitude between our data and Fukunaga and Goda's model can perhaps be attributed to the choice of a constant factor 2 in place of the more usual 4.2 [11,12] in the denominator of equations (1) and (2), or to lack of precision in the value of the fiber diameter d_f employed herein ($3 \mu\text{m}$). The discrepancy in the dependency of K on f_s , however, can only be due to a difference in the f_s dependence of S_o (equation (2)) between our and their experiments. Using experimental data given in figures 3-a and 3-b, and from equation (2), S_o can be plotted as a function of the volume fraction solid f_s formed in the matrix during infiltration, figure 7. S_o is seen to increase as f_s increases, contrary to Fukunaga and Goda's model in which S_o decreases with increasing f_s (or V_s). This implies that the morphology of the solid phase formed in these experiments differs from that in the experiments of Fukunaga and Goda.

The reason for the discrepancy may be due to the lesser purity of the aluminum employed in this work (99.9%) compared to the 99.99% pure Al used by Fukunaga and Goda [7]. The

Figure 8 - Solidification model yielding an increase in the surface area per volume of solid in the composite as the volume fraction of solid metal increases.

Figure 7 - Plot of the area per volume of solid phases present in the composite during infiltration of a cold fiber preform from equation (2) and the data given in figures 3-a and 3-b.

Figure 9- Temperature and fraction solid profile in the composite during infiltration of a cold preform by superheated metal, assuming no heat conduction.

presence of small amounts of solute in a metal can exert a strong influence on the morphology of the growing solid [13]. If solute must diffuse in the liquid phase away from the liquid-solid interface, the formation of a uniform layer of solid metal surrounding the fibers is inhibited [14, 15, 16]. A solidification sequence such as that in figure 8 would then yield a rapid increase in S_O with increasing f_s in agreement with the data in figure 7.

B- Effect of metal superheat. If the metal temperature T_M is significantly above its melting point T_m , heat supplied by the incoming metal by conduction and convection will remelt the solid formed in the composite at the infiltration front. This remelting must take place at a well-defined position L' , because no heat can be transported and hence no gradients in f_s are possible within the semi-solid matrix region of the composite. If we neglect heat conduction through the metal and the composite upstream of L' , the temperature profile is as given in figure 9. This assumption simplifies considerably the mathematics involved in calculating L' , and yields a minimum value for L' , since the contribution of heat conduction from the metal upstream can only increase L' . Writing a heat balance at L' over a short time period dt , inserting equation (4) and integrating from $L=0$ to L yields:

$$\frac{L'}{L} = \frac{(1 - V_f) c_m \rho_m (T_M - T_m)}{(\rho_f c_f V_f + \rho_m c_m (1 - V_f))(T_M - T_m) + c_f \rho_f V_f (T_m - T_f)} \quad (5)$$

where $c_c = \rho_m c_m (1 - V_f) + \rho_f c_f V_f$. The presence of superheat will therefore increase the overall specific permeability of the infiltrated composite, roughly by a factor $(1 - L'/L)$ since the specific permeability of the fiber preform with no solid metal present is, according to equation (2), much higher than that measured in the preform with solid metal present, figures 3-a and 3-b. Calculating $(1 - L'/L)$ from equation (5), and comparing the resulting permeability for $T_M - T_m = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_M - T_m = 100^\circ\text{C}$, an increase in K by a factor 1.5 results. This is in rough agreement with the data given in figure 3-c and explains the weak dependence of permeability and infiltration length on superheat.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A device was developed allowing independent control of processing parameters in the infiltration of fiber-reinforced metals. In particular, the position of the metal front during infiltration can be monitored continuously.
2. Measurements of the permeability and infiltration length indicate a strong dependence on fiber volume fraction and fiber temperature, and a weaker dependence on metal temperature.
3. Results of permeability measurements indicate a solidification mechanism that differs from the uniform fiber coating mechanism proposed by other investigators. This is attributed to the lower purity of the metal matrix in this work.
4. Experimental evidence indicates that in the presence of metal superheat, solid metal formed at the infiltration front remelts over a distance L' in the composite. A simple lower bound estimation of L' is proposed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We gratefully acknowledge the support of the Innovative Science and Technology Division of SDIO, the Office of Naval Research, General Motors Corporation, and ALCOA. We also thank ICI for providing the reinforcements used in this research. We extend our gratitude to Dr. J.T. Blucher for help in the design and fabrication of the apparatus used in this research. We also thank Ms. Maria Wehrle-Due, Mr. Pedro Almeida and Mr. Terrence Wong for help with producing the samples.

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